

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.*	Colour	μ_{eff} B.M.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			
			M	N	S	Cl/Br
BPTC	Yellowish white	—	—	16.26 (16.34)	12.4 (12.5)	—
Cu(BPTC) ₂ Cl ₂	Steel grey	1.67	9.19 (9.28)	12.12 (12.27)	9.21 (9.34)	10.26 (10.37)
Cu(BPTC) ₂ Br ₂	Grey	1.69	8.50 (8.61)	11.81 (11.98)	8.51 (8.67)	21.57 (21.69)
Cu(BPTC) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	Green	1.84	8.32 (8.40)	18.40 (18.52)	8.32 (8.47)	—
Cu(BPTC) ₂ (ClO ₄) ₂	Greenish yellow	1.90	7.09 (7.18)	9.23 (9.49)	7.10 (7.23)	7.91 (8.03)
Co(BPTC) ₂ Cl ₂	Bluish white	4.50	7.64 (7.88)	11.01 (11.17)	8.34 (8.51)	9.23 (9.44)
Co(BPTC) ₂ Br ₂	Faint blue	4.57	8.10 (8.24)	11.52 (11.74)	8.63 (8.95)	22.12 (22.38)
Co(BPTC) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	Olive green	4.70	8.30 (8.45)	16.00 (16.07)	9.00 (9.18)	—
Co(BPTC) ₂ (ClO ₄) ₂	Dark yellow	4.75	7.50 (7.63)	10.62 (10.83)	8.10 (8.29)	9.00 (9.19)
Ni(BPTC) ₂ Cl ₂	Canary yellow	2.98	8.90 (9.13)	12.92 (13.06)	9.61 (9.95)	10.90 (11.04)
Ni(BPTC) ₂ Br ₂	Brown	2.99	6.90 (7.04)	9.80 (10.08)	7.41 (7.68)	19.10 (19.21)
Ni(BPTC) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	Pale violet	3.10	7.10 (7.29)	13.7 (13.91)	7.63 (7.95)	—
Ni(BPTC) ₂ (ClO ₄) ₂	Violet	3.30	6.50 (6.70)	9.50 (9.60)	7.21 (7.34)	8.00 (8.14)

*BPTC = C₁₁H₁₁ON₂S.

having values in the range 2.98–3.3 B.M. is indicative of octahedral structure. The Co^{II} complexes have values in the range 4.5–4.75 B.M. which can also be assigned to octahedral structure. The complexes of Cu^{II} show a broad band around 14 280 cm⁻¹ which can be assigned to the transition, ²E_g → ²T_{2g}. Besides, a band around 25 000 cm⁻¹ exists which may be due to charge transfer band. The complexes of Co^{II} exhibit two bands at 9 100 and 18 900 cm⁻¹ which may be assigned to the transitions, ⁴T_{1g}(F) → ⁴T_{2g}(F) (ν₁) and ⁴T_{1g}(F) → ⁴T_{1g}(P) (ν₂) respectively, in an approximately octahedral field^{1,2}. A charge transfer band is also observed at 27 000 cm⁻¹. The complexes of Ni^{II} exhibit three well-resolved bands at 9 800, 16 400 and 25 800 cm⁻¹ attributed to ³A_{2g}(F) → ³T_{2g}(F) (ν₁), ³A_{2g}(F) → ³T_{1g}(F) (ν₂) and ³A_{2g}(F) → ³T_{1g}(P) (ν₃) transitions respectively under an octahedral environment around Ni^{II} ion^{1,2}.

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Studies on the Stability of some Binary and Ternary Complexes of Nickel(II), Copper(II) and Zinc(II)

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BINARY complexes of some bivalent metal ions with oxydiacetic acid (ODAA) have been reported¹⁻⁴. A survey of the literature has revealed that mixed ligand complexes of Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} with ODAA as primary ligand, and maleic acid (MALEA), malonic acid (MALNA) and phthalic acid (PHA) as secondary ligands have not been studied so far. In view of the above, it was considered of interest to determine the formation constants of binary and ternary complexes of Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} ions with the above ligands.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. The pH-titrations were carried out at 25 ± 0.5° using

a Philips PR-9405 pH meter in aqueous medium (accuracy ± 0.02 pH).

The following sets of solutions, each of initial volume 50 ml and ionic strength $\mu = 0.1$ M (NaClO_4), were prepared and pH-metrically titrated with a standard solution of 0.25 M NaOH: (a) 2.5×10^{-3} M HClO_4 , (b) 2.5×10^{-3} M $\text{HClO}_4 + 5 \times 10^{-4}$ M ligand (primary) + 5×10^{-4} M metal ion (Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , or Zn^{II}), and (c) (a) $+ 5 \times 10^{-4}$ M ODAA + 5×10^{-4} M secondary ligands + 5×10^{-4} M metal ion. Some representation data are presented in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Potentiometric curves for nickel: (a) HClO_4 , (b) $\text{Ni}^{II} + (\text{a}) + \text{ODAA}$, (c) MALEA + (b), (d) MALNA + (b), and (e) PHA + (b).

Results and Discussion

The dissociation constants of the ligands were evaluated by Irving and Rossotti method⁶. The formation constants of the binary and ternary complexes were calculated by the method of Ramamoorthy and Santapa^{8,9}. The refined^{8,9} values are stated in Table 1.

TABLE 1—FORMATION CONSTANTS* OF BINARY AND TERNARY COMPLEXES

System	log K_{MA}	System	log K_{MAB}
$\text{Ni}^{II} - \text{ODAA}$	3.32		
$\text{Cu}^{II} - \text{ODAA}$	3.80		
$\text{Zn}^{II} - \text{ODAA}$	3.52		
$\text{Ni}^{II} - \text{MALEA}$	2.00	$\text{Ni}^{II} - \text{ODAA} - \text{MALEA}$	7.32
$\text{Cu}^{II} - \text{MALEA}$	2.88	$\text{Zn}^{II} - \text{ODAA} - \text{MALEA}$	7.56
$\text{Zn}^{II} - \text{MALEA}$	2.00		
$\text{Ni}^{II} - \text{MALNA}$	3.24	$\text{Ni}^{II} - \text{ODAA} - \text{MALNA}$	5.48
$\text{Cu}^{II} - \text{MALNA}$	4.10	$\text{Cu}^{II} - \text{ODAA} - \text{MALNA}$	7.78
$\text{Zn}^{II} - \text{MALNA}$	2.96	$\text{Zn}^{II} - \text{ODAA} - \text{MALNA}$	6.76
$\text{Ni}^{II} - \text{PHA}$	2.17	$\text{Ni}^{II} - \text{ODAA} - \text{PHA}$	5.41
$\text{Cu}^{II} - \text{PHA}$	2.50	$\text{Cu}^{II} - \text{ODAA} - \text{PHA}$	6.75
$\text{Zn}^{II} - \text{PHA}$	2.20		

pK^H: ODAA (2.84, 4.94), MALEA (1.91, 5.52), MALNA (2.70, 5.02), PHA (2.81, 4.74). *Limits of error = $\pm 0.02 - 0.23$ in log units.

The potentiometric curves for all the metals were found to be very similar in nature and hence the curves of only one metal ion (Ni^{II}) are shown in

Fig. 1. For curve (a), inflection occurs at $m = 5.0$, therefore, for curve (b), the inflection is counted to take place at $m = 2[(7.0 - 5.0)]$. It indicates the formation of 1 : 1 complex in $\text{Ni}^{II} - \text{ODAA}$ system (m being the number of moles of base added per mole of metal ion or ligand). The curves (c-e) represent 1 : 1 : 1 ternary complex system, for which inflections were observed at $m = 4[(9.0 - 5.0)]$. These 1 : 1 : 1 ternary complexes result from stepwise addition of ligands to the metal ion. The formation of heteroligand-metal complexes in these systems is further evidenced by lowering in pH in comparison with the binary versus ternary systems, and non-appearance of solid phase during titration. The order of stability of ternary complexes in terms of metal ions and ligands are: $\text{Ni}^{II} < \text{Cu}^{II} > \text{Zn}^{II}$; MALEA > MALNA > PHA (for Ni^{II}) and MALEA > MALNA (for Zn^{II}). The maximum stability of ternary complexes of maleic acid may be due to the presence of a double bond which increases the stability due to exocyclic conjugation.

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Nickel(II), Copper(II) and Manganese(II) Complexes with Tetradentate Schiff Bases and Neutral Ligands

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THE Schiff base complexes of transition metal ions possess unusual configuration¹ and structural lability and are sensitive to molecular environment. Generally, the stable stereochemistries are